

The Alzheimer's Disease Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Portal

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ABSTRACT

The Target Enablement to Accelerate Therapy Development in Alzheimer's Disease (TREAT-AD) Center at Indiana School of Medicine and Purdue provides cutting-edge research aimed at drug discovery for the crippling disease. It consists of five core activities: medicinal chemistry, structural biology, high throughput screening, bioinformatics, and administration and data management. To enable these essential activities, the Cyberinfrastructure Integration Research Center (CIRC) at Indiana University has created the Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Portal (BCB Portal). This science gateway provides a repository for tools and data used by researchers at TREAT-AD. The BCB Portal integrates data management, diverse computational resources, visualization tools, publicly accessible user interfaces, and secure researcher interfaces. Currently, the BCB Portal is active. Several bioinformatics applications have been integrated into the Apache Airavata Framework to leverage its robust features, including data management, resource provisioning, application porting, and user-centric design. We will also provide a look at the drug discovery process, identifying target drugs, computational analysis of those targets, and finally, the final output of the TREAT-AD Center target enablement packages (TEPs). These TEPs allow promising compounds to move to laboratory and clinical testing. The initial conceptualization of the BCB Portal was presented at Gateways 2020, and this lightning talk will cover the implementation of those concepts over the past year.

Keywords—Alzheimer's Disease, Science Gateways, Bioinformatics, Apache Airavata